

***In vitro* kinetics as a cornerstone for QIVIVE and IVIVE**

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Abstract

The free drug hypothesis postulates that only free drug molecules can interact with biological molecules, having substantial implications in the fields of toxicokinetics and toxicodynamics. It implies that the ideal dose metric for extrapolations between biological models, specifically in In Vitro to In Vivo Extrapolation (IVIVE) and Quantitative In Vitro to In Vivo Extrapolation (QIVIVE), is the concentration of free drug at the target site, whether it be specific tissues or cells.

Physiologically Based Kinetic (PBK) models are crucial, allowing the simulation of in vivo kinetics processes to ascertain the free concentration at the target site in time. Although the in vitro environment is inherently simpler, various factors within it, including binding to serum proteins or lipids, adhesion to plastic, and evaporation, significantly influence the availability of test chemicals. In recent years, recognition of these in vitro kinetic processes has increased in the scientific community, as multiple in silico models have emerged to predict these in vitro kinetic processes. These models integrate with a variety of compartments and processes, and while some of these models focus on specific chemicals using experimental data fitting, others opt for a broader approach, leveraging Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationships

(QSARs) to predict partition coefficients or rates. Examples will be provided to demonstrate the application of these in vitro kinetic models, not only in identifying optimal dose metrics in vitro models subject to repeated exposure but also in extrapolating in vitro-derived kinetic parameters to in vivo scenarios.

However, the applicability domains of these models of in vitro kinetics, both biologically and chemically, are limited. Notable gaps exist, particularly for advanced in vitro models like those deployed in the EU-funded ONTOX project and chemicals that remain unexplored within the QSAR training sets. Expanding the applicability domains of these models is crucial for the accuracy of IVIVE and QIVIVE, particularly in initiatives such as ONTOX, fulfilling the promise of Next Generation Risk Assessment.